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Analysis of the Use of Pharmacy Graduates in Task-Shifting as an Alternative Management Strategy in Healthcare Organizations

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Abstract

The shortage of health care professionals and large patient load in developing countries like India, leads to large burden in healthcare system, resulting in impediment to optimum patient care. This leads to degradation in healthcare service quality. Based on our analysis, the data collected from 532 subjects reveals that only 7.01% of the subjects have received counselling always, 59.65% thinks counselling should be given and only 41.66% are satisfied with current healthcare system. This concludes that there is a scarcity of optimum patient care in the country for many chronic diseases. Hence a quick optimum solution is needed to address the critical shortage of trained healthcare professionals and it is found that Task shifting is an optimum alternate solution to address such acute shortage of professionally qualified healthcare workers in developing countries. In Task-shifting model, task acceptors should be a paramedical or pharmacy professional who can be trained quickly to treat the patients. In India, Pharmacists being ignored professions in healthcare system have crucial role to play between the prescriber and the patients. Pharmacy graduates could be used as medicine prescribers as in other developed countries as addition rather than substitution. This paper contains the analysis of the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the use of pharmacy graduates for task-shifting by healthcare organizations as alternative survival strategy. Factors influencing the various determinant issues of task shifting according to identified key attributes under four constructs are derived and the critical constituent elements (CCE) of these factors are listed and analysed.

Keywords: Task shifting in healthcare organization, Pharmacy graduates, Alternative strategy, Optimum patient care, Factor and elemental analysis of Task shifting.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Many developing countries are facing a crisis in human health resources due to a critical shortage of healthcare workers. This shortage is compounded by a high burden of infectious diseases, emigration of trained professionals, difficult working conditions, and low motivation by country governments. Consequently, for example, the burden of chronic diseases like HIV/AIDS has led to the concept of task shifting between healthcare workers and being increasingly promoted as a way of rapidly expanding human resource capability. Such process refers to the delegation of health and medical service responsibilities from higher to lower cadres of health staff, and in some cases even to non-professionals [1-2]. The delegation of tasks from one cadre to another, previously often called substitution [3], is not a new concept. It has been used in many countries and for many decades, either as requirements to emergency needs or as a method to provide adequate healthcare service at primary and secondary levels, especially in rural and urban health centres with understaffed facilities, and also to enhance quality and reduce costs [4]. However, rapidly increasing the need of healthcare generated by the HIV/AIDS epidemic, accelerating trained human resource crises, and unrest in many African countries, which contribute to the collapse or near-collapse of public health systems and increasing health service inequalities to the needy patients within and between countries, have given the solution in the form of the concept and practice of task shifting as new prominence and urgency. Gaps are still existing with respect to the health programmes, which are unevenly delivered for needy people, with rural areas being particularly under-serviced, insufficient support for healthcare in healthcare services, and irregular and inconsistent identification and treatment of more common communicable diseases. This leads to the suggestion of strengthening the concept of task shifting to skilled people available in relative/paramedical areas. The World Health Organization advocates a quick solution to the stated deficiency of professional health workers by means of task-shifting, the process of transferring clinical care responsibilities from more specialized professionals to less specialized health workers through proper delegation, as a strategy to realize the United Nations Millennium Development Goals [2]. For example, it is estimated that sub-Saharan African countries need to triple their current health workforce in order to bring up it close to reach the level as expected by the Health Millennium Development Goals [5]. Accordingly, by shifting the task of providing health services from higher to lower cadres of health staff based on providing sufficient training to handle the situations, the organizations and the countries can find solutions to the shortage of health workers. More precisely, Task Shifting describes a situation where a patient care task normally carried out by a physician is transferred to a health professional with a different but related or lower level of education and training, or to a person trained specifically to perform a limited task only for a short period, without having a formal health education. The rationale behind the concept of applying task shifting idea in developing countries is that the alternative would be no care as health systems are impeded by the shortage of growing health workforce and imbalance in

the distribution [6]. Innovative solutions are therefore required to quickly expand the health workforce in an emergency to meet the demand to care for chronic disease. In this article, we study and discuss the growing evidence in support of expanding work force strategies for chronic disease management in developing countries like India. In this paper, instead of using trained nurses and lay-people (family members and friends) as peer supporters as studied in many task shifting research studies, we have suggested to use paramedical professionals like pharmacists to extend the education and follow-up of patients with chronic diseases beyond clinical settings and improve adherence and treatment outcomes. Alternative strategy concept is suggested in even social sciences where based on cost/benefit analysis one can follow alternative strategy than the suggested strategy to solve a problem [7-11].

Figure 1: Block diagram to represent Alternative Strategy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW :

Task-shifting is officially accepted and further suggested by World Health Organization during 2007 and developed global recommendations and guidelines on its website on Task-shifting: rational redistribution of tasks among health workforce teams: global recommendations and guidelines [12-16]. Thereafter, a number of research papers have been published on Task-shifting in the healthcare sector. During the year 2008, McPake, et al [17] published an article on Task-shifting in Healthcare in resource-poor countries and Zimmerman, et al [18] have published an article on Task-shifting and innovative medical education--moving outside the box to serve rural Nepal. During the year 2009, Lehmann, et al worked on Task-shifting: the answer to the human resources crisis in Africa [19], Morris, et al studied Use of task-shifting to rapidly scale-up HIV treatment services: experiences from Lusaka [20], Shumbusho et al studied Task-shifting for scale-up of HIV care: evaluation of nurse-centered antiretroviral treatment at rural health centers in Rwanda [21], De Brouwere et al studied Task-shifting for emergency obstetric surgery in district hospitals in Senegal [22], and Chu et al studied surgical Task-shifting in sub-Saharan Africa [23]. During the year 2010, Lekoubou et al studied Hypertension, diabetes mellitus and Task-shifting in their management in sub-Saharan Africa [24], McCollum et al made a retrospective observational study on Task-shifting routine inpatient pediatric HIV testing improves program outcomes in urban Malawi [25], and Callaghan et al made a systematic review of task-shifting for HIV treatment and care in Africa [26]. During the year 2011, Ivers et al

studied Task-shifting in HIV care: a case study of nurse-centered community-based care in rural Haiti [27], Gessesew et al [28] studied Task-shifting and sharing in Tigray, Ethiopia, to achieve comprehensive emergency obstetric care, and Nabudere et al studied Task-shifting in maternal and child Healthcare : an evidence brief for Uganda [29].

During the year 2012, Dambisya et al published a Case study on policy and programmatic implications of Task-shifting in Uganda [30], Ferrinho et al studied Task-shifting: experiences and opinions of health workers in Mozambique and Zambia [31], Ford et al made a systematic review and meta-analysis on Safety of task-shifting for male medical circumcision [32], Mdege et al [33] studied the effectiveness and cost implications of task-shifting in the delivery of antiretroviral therapy to HIV-infected patients, and Buttorff et al studied economic evaluation of a task-shifting intervention for common mental disorders in India [34]. During the year 2013, Dawson et al studied Task-shifting and sharing in maternal and reproductive health in low-income countries: a narrative synthesis of current evidence [35], Guilbert et al studied challenges of implementing task-shifting in contraceptive care an experience in Quebec, Canada [36], and the FIGO Committee for the Ethical Aspects of Human Reproduction developed a policy for task-shifting in obstetric care [37]. Iwu et al [38] studied Task-shifting of HIV management from doctors to nurses in Africa: Clinical outcomes and evidence on nurse self-efficacy and job satisfaction, Joshi et al made a systematic review on Task-shifting for non-communicable disease management in low and middle income countries [39], Kredo et al made a study on Task-shifting from doctors to non- doctors for initiation and maintenance of antiretroviral therapy [40].

During the year 2015, Maier et al studied the role of governance in implementing task-shifting from physicians to nurses in advanced roles in Europe, US, Canada, New Zealand and Australia [41], Gichangi et al studied Task-shifting for eye care by giving responsibility to general nurses as trichiasis surgeons in Kenya, Malawi, and Tanzania [42], Crowley et al studied trends in Task-shifting in HIV treatment in Africa: Effectiveness, challenges, and acceptability to the health professions [43], Agyapong et al studied Task-shifting of mental Healthcare services in Ghana: ease of referral, perception, and concerns of stakeholders about quality of care [44], Jayasekera et al studied task-shifting as an approach to decentralized treatment of hepatitis C patients in medically underserved areas [45]. Gupta et al studied Task-shifting in surgery: lessons from an Indian Heart Hospital [46], Akinyemi et al studied task-shifting training improves stroke knowledge among Nigerian non-neurologist health workers [47], and Bhushan et al studied Task-shifting: A key strategy in the multipronged approach to reduce maternal mortality in India [48].

During the year 2016, Maier et al made a comparatively study on Task-shifting from physicians to nurses in primary care in 39 countries: a cross-country [49], Santos et al, published an overview of the mental health system in Mozambique: addressing the treatment gap with a task-shifting strategy in primary care [50], Jayasekera et al studied a case for Task-shifting on Hepatitis C treatment delivery mandates optimizing available Healthcare human resources [51], Some et al studied Task-shifting the management of non-communicable diseases to nurses in Kibera, Kenya [52], Hadorn et al studied task-shifting using a Pain Management Protocol in an Emergency Care Service: Nurses' Perception through the Eye of the Rogers's Diffusion of Innovation Theory [53], Yoo et al studied task-shifting-A practical strategy to improve the global access to treatment for chronic hepatitis C [54], and Kayingo et al studied Task-shifting and capacity building for non-communicable diseases in Uganda [55], Gyamfi et al studied a mixed-methods of training nurses in task-shifting strategies for the management and control of hypertension in Ghana [56], Bischoff et

al studied the Experiences of Task-shifting to Reduce Mental Health Disparities in Underserved, Rural Communities [57], Magidson et al studied Task-shifting and Delivery of Behavioral Medicine Interventions in Resource-Poor Global Settings: HIV/AIDS Treatment in sub-Saharan Africa [58], Iwelunmor et al exploring stakeholders' perceptions of a task-shifting strategy for hypertension control in Ghana: a qualitative study [59], Keller et al studied task-shifting impact of introducing a pilot community health worker cadre into Zambia's public sector health workforce [60], Sanyahumbi et al studied Task-shifting to clinical officer-led echocardiography screening for detecting rheumatic heart disease in Malawi, Africa [61]. Landes et al studied Task-shifting of triage to peer expert informal care providers at a tertiary referral HIV clinic in Malawi: a cross-sectional operational evaluation [62], Kattakuzhy et al made a Nonrandomized Clinical Trial expansion of Treatment for Hepatitis C Virus Infection by Task-shifting to Community-based Nonspecialist Providers [63], Galárraga et al made a cost-benefit analysis of task-shifting alcohol interventions for HIV+ persons in Kenya [64], Okyere et al analysed task-shifting as a solution to the health workers' shortage in Northern Ghana [65], Aithal Architha et al made an Empirical Study on the Importance of Task-shifting in Current Healthcare System [66], Aithal Architha et al also made a study on Task-shifting: A Need for Current Healthcare System [67], Mumtaz et al analysed a question does Task-shifting among parts of a weak health system help? [68], Spies et al made an exploratory descriptive study on Task-shifting in East Africa [69], and Mbeye et al made a systematic review and meta-analysis on Shifting tasks from pharmacy to non-pharmacy personnel for providing antiretroviral therapy to people living with HIV [70].

Task-Shifting Systematic Review:

A systematic review on task-shifting is carried out for HIV treatment and care in Africa by Callaghan, M. Et al. during 2010 [71]. They reviewed 84 core articles out of 2960 articles falling into the related area, 51 reported outcomes, including research from 10 countries in sub-Saharan Africa and concluded that Task-shifting is an effective strategy for addressing shortages of human resource in HIV treatment and care. According to them, Task-shifting offers cost-effective, high-quality care to many patients than a physician-centered model. The major implementation challenges include availability of paramedical staff, adequate and sustainable training, support and pay for staff in new roles, the integration of new members into healthcare teams, and the compliance of local regulatory bodies. Thus their study suggested that careful implementation should be essential in Task-shifting where human resources shortages threaten the rollout programmes [71].

Fulton, B. D., et al reviewed the health workforce skill mix and Task-shifting in low income countries [72]. The review provides substantial evidence that Task-shifting is an important policy option to help acute workforce shortages and skill mix imbalances. It also suggested Task-shifting is promising, challenging and compare the results of the new cadre with the traditional cadre and concluded that Task-shifting is a promising policy option to increase the productive efficiency of the delivery of Healthcare services, increasing the number of services provided at a given quality and cost [72].

During 2012, Emdin, C. A., et al [73] carried out a systematic review evaluating the impact of Task-shifting on access to antiretroviral therapy (ART) in sub-Saharan Africa. They defined Task-shifting as the shifting of antiretroviral therapy initiation and management from physicians to nurses and proposed it as a possible method to increase access to HIV treatment in Sub-Saharan Africa. They identified 25 articles which evaluated the effect of Task-shifting and found that Task-shifting increases access, even though the studies were of low

methodological quality. They concluded that Task-shifting appears to be most effective at increasing access when combined with other interventions and financial support [73].

A systematic review on the effectiveness and cost implications of task-shifting in the delivery of antiretroviral therapy to HIV-infected patients is also conducted by Mdege, N. D., et al during 2012 [74]. As per their study, Task-shifting resulted in substantial cost and physician time savings and concluded that task-shifting from doctors to nurses, or from healthcare professionals to lay health workers can potentially reduce costs of antiretroviral therapy provision without compromising health outcomes for patients. Task-shifting is, therefore, a potentially effective and cost-effective approach to address the human resource limitations to antiretroviral therapy rollout [74].

Another systematic review and meta-analysis is done on Safety of task-shifting for male medical circumcision by Ford, N., et al during 2012 [75]. By using the published data up to July 2012 and found ten suitable studies and concluded that Task-shifting of male medical circumcision to non-physician clinicians can be done safely, with reported rates of adverse events similar to doctors and specialists [75].

A systematic review of qualitative evidence on barriers and facilitators to the implementation of task-shifting in midwifery services is conducted by Colvin, C. J., et al during 2013 [76] by including thirty-seven studies to find (1) challenges in defining and defending the midwifery model of care during Task-shifting, (2) training, supervision and support challenges in midwifery Task-shifting, and (3) teamwork and Task-shifting and concluded that Task-shifting may serve as a powerful means to address the crisis in human resources for maternal and newborn health, it is also a complex intervention that generally requires careful planning, implementation and ongoing supervision and support to ensure optimal and safe impact [76].

In another review done during 2013, Padmanathan, et al [77] studied the acceptability and feasibility of task-sharing for mental healthcare in low and middle income countries both qualitative and quantitative data were extracted and reviewed using a comparative thematic analysis. In total, 21 studies were included, nine of which were of strong or adequate quality and twelve of unknown quality. The review highlighted that task-sharing is not an outright solution for overcoming human resource shortages in low and middle income countries. A number of factors need to be considered in order for task-sharing to be acceptable and feasible, for example, the incidence of distress experienced by the task-sharing workforce, their self-perceived level of competence, the acceptance of the workforce by other Healthcare professionals and the incentives provided to ensure workforce retention [77].

A systematic review on Task-shifting for Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) Management in Low and Middle Income Countries is carried out by Joshi, R., et al during 2014 [39]. They reviewed 22 articles related to Task-shifting and found that tasks performed by nonphysician health workers (NPHWs) included screening for NCDs and providing primary healthcare. The majority of studies showed improved health outcomes when compared with usual healthcare, including reductions in blood pressure, increased uptake of medications and lower depression scores. Factors such as training of NPHWs, provision of algorithms and protocols for screening, treatment, and drug titration were the main enablers of the task-shifting intervention. The main constraints identified were restrictions on prescribing medications and availability of medicines. They also demonstrated that task-shifting was cost-effective [39]. They concluded that task-shifting from physicians to NPHWs, if accompanied by health system re-structuring is a potentially effective and affordable strategy for improving access to healthcare for NCDs.

Ogedegbe, G., et al during 2014 [78] reviewed randomised controlled trials of Task-shifting interventions for cardiovascular risk reduction in low-income and middle-income countries and concluded that effective task-shifting interventions targeted at reducing the global cardiovascular disease (CVD) epidemic in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) are urgently needed [78].

Another systematic review on Task-shifting for the delivery of pediatric antiretroviral treatment is published by Penazzato, M., et al during 2014 [79] on Task-shifting for the delivery of pediatric antiretroviral treatment. Five databases and two conferences were searched from inception till August 01, 2013. Eight observational studies provided outcome data for 11,828 children who received ART from non-physician providers across 10 countries in sub-Saharan Africa. They suggested that Task-shifting of ART care can result in outcomes comparable to routine physician care, and this approach should be considered as part of a strategy to scale-up paediatric treatment. They also suggested that specialist care should remain important for management of sick patients and complicated cases [79].

A systematic review was conducted by Martínez-González, N. A., et al during 2015 [80] to compare resource utilization with task-shifting from physicians to nurses in primary care [80]. Literature searches yielded 4,589 citations. Twenty studies comprising 13,171 participants met the inclusion criteria. Meta-analyses showed nurses had more return consultations and longer consultations than physicians but were similar in their use of referrals, prescriptions, or investigations. The evidence has limitations but suggests that the effects may be influenced by the utilization of resources, context of care, available guidance, and supervision. Cost data suggest physician–nurse salary and physician’s time spent on supervision and delegation are important components of nurse-led care costs.

Another systematic review on the impact of physician–nurse Task-shifting in primary care on the course of a disease is published by Martínez-González, N. A., et al during 2015 [81]. In their study, they used twelve randomized controlled trials (RCTs) comprising 22,617 randomized patients conducted mainly in Europe. Nurse-led care was delivered mainly by nurse practitioners following structured protocols and validated instruments. 84 % of the result showed no significant differences between nurse-led care and physician-led care, nurses achieved better outcomes in the secondary prevention of heart disease and a greater positive effect in managing dyspepsia and at lowering cardiovascular risk in diabetic patients [81]. The review concluded that the trained nurses may have the ability to achieve outcome results that are at least similar to physicians’ for managing the course of disease.

Polus, S., et al published a review paper [82] during 2015, identified six randomized controlled trials published between 1977 and 1995 that assessed the safety and effectiveness of Task-shifting for the delivery of long-term contraceptives. Two studies assessed intrauterine devices (IUD) insertion by nurses compared to doctors, two assessed IUD insertion by auxiliary nurse-midwives compared to doctors, one assessed tubal ligation by midwives compared to doctors, and one assessed the delivery of vasectomy by medical students compared to doctors. They did not find any difference in contraceptive outcomes between cadres. The results showed that Task-shifting for the delivery of long-term contraceptives may be a safe and effective approach to increasing access to contraception [82].

Crowley, T., et al. [83] studied database on Task-shifting for HIV treatment between 2009 and 2014. Their evidence suggests that Task-shifting is an effective strategy for addressing human resource constraints in healthcare systems in many countries and provides a cost-effective approach without compromising patient outcomes. The strategy generally seems to

be accepted by the health professions although several arguments against Task-shifting as a long-term approach have been raised. Based on their study, they concluded that Task-shifting occurs in many settings other than HIV treatment programmes and is viewed as a key strategy for governing human resources for healthcare [83].

The review conducted by Federspiel et al [84], surgical Task-shifting occurred in 30 (33%) of 92 countries and interpreted that Task-shifting is used to augment the global surgical workforce across all geographical regions and income groups. Associate clinicians are ubiquitous among the global surgical workforce and should be considered in plans to scale up the surgical workforce in countries with workforce shortages.

During 2016, Lee et al [85] conducted a narrative review of published comparative clinical trials that evaluated efficacy or effectiveness of clinic-based cardiovascular disease (CVD) prevention and management quality improvement interventions in LMICs. From 847 articles identified in the electronic search, 49 met full inclusion criteria and were selected for review. Selected studies were performed in 19 different LMICs. There were 10 studies of system level quality improvement interventions, 38 studies of patient/provider interventions, and one study that fit both criteria and suggest that CVD care quality improvement can be successfully implemented in LMICs.

A Cross-country comparative research, based on an international expert survey, plus literature scoping review is made by Maier et al [86]. A total of 93 country experts participated, covering Europe, USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand. Task-shifting, where nurses take up advanced roles from physicians, was implemented in two-thirds of countries. Many countries have implemented task-shifting reforms to maximise workforce capacity. Reforms have focused on removing regulatory and to a lower extent, financial barriers, yet were often lengthy and controversial.

The systematic review published by Seidman et al [87] investigates whether Task-shifting in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) results in efficiency improvements by achieving cost savings. The study identified 794 articles, of which 34 were included in their study. They found that substantial evidence exists for achieving cost savings and efficiency improvements from Task-shifting activities related to tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS, and additional evidence exists for the potential to achieve cost savings from activities related to malaria, NCDs, NTDs, childhood illness, and other disease areas, especially at the primary healthcare and community levels. The study concluded that Task-shifting presents a viable option for health system cost savings in LMICs and Task-shifting can improve population health and health systems efficiency in their countries [87].

During 2017, Mbeye et al [88] conducted comprehensive searches of peer-reviewed and gray literature. Three studies with 1993 participants met the inclusion criteria, including two cluster trials conducted in Kenya and Uganda and an individually randomised trial conducted in Brazil. They found very low certainty evidence regarding mortality due to the low number of events. Therefore, they are uncertain whether there is a true increase in mortality as the effect size suggests or a reduction in mortality between pharmacy and non-pharmacy models of dispensing ART.

The above elaborative review results on Task-shifting inspired to study the nature of strategy involved in Task-shifting of healthcare services in developing countries.

3. OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY OF PRESENT STUDY :

This type of study is necessary to align investment in human resources for health care services with the current and future needs of the population and of health systems, taking account of the supply market dynamics and education policies of the country, to address the shortages and improve distribution of health workers, so as to enable maximum improvements in health outcomes, social welfare, employment creation, and economic growth.

In the present study, the following objectives are identified.

- To check present satisfaction level of current healthcare system in India and to assess gaps in the healthcare system, in order to fulfill the needs of the patients who are suffering from chronic diseases and to find out the importance of task shifting.
- The possibility of using task-shifting model as alternative strategy to solve problem.
- The possibility of using pharmacy graduates as addition rather than substitution for clinical diagnostics and for prescription of medicine to address such acute shortage of professionally qualified healthcare workers.
- The analysis of affecting factors under advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of use of pharmacy graduates for task-shifting by healthcare organizations as an alternative survival strategy.

To check the present satisfaction level of patients about the current healthcare system in India we used empirical survey method based on online questionnaires and the results are analysed using Microsoft EXCEL 2010. The possibility of using pharmacy graduates in task-shifting in India is studied by analysing their curriculum both at the undergraduate and postgraduate level and using another empirical survey method, the type, time period, and kind of training to be provided to take up such responsibility. Finally, by using ABCD model analysis method, the affecting factors of using pharmacy graduates for task-shifting under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages for some identified key attributes. Finally, the critical constituent elements of using pharmacy graduates for task-shifting by healthcare organizations as alternative survival strategy are listed.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

The data collected from 532 subjects reveals that only 7.01% of the subjects have received counseling always; 57.01% have received the counseling sometimes while 14.91% have been counseled mostly, and 19.3% has never been counseled. Results of the survey reveal that out of the population, only 14.4% have been counseled more than 10 minutes while 37.3% have been counseled within 1-5 minutes and 21.05% have been counseled less than a minute as shown in figure 2 and counseling time per session by physicians as per out survey is shown in figure 3.

Fig. 2 : Counseling frequency of patients by physicians

Fig. 3: Counseling time per session by physicians

Fig. 4 : Satisfaction level of current healthcare system

Fig. 5: Deficiency in the current health system as per out survey.

Out of them, 59.65% think that counseling should be given and only 41.66% are satisfied with current health care system while 56.57% are not satisfied. According to 42.1% of the general population, the current health care system is lacking in patient counseling and 19.29% patient care as given in figure 3. The deficiency in the current health system as per out survey is shown in figure 4 can be resolved using the task shifting proposal using paramedical practitioners. Task shifting requires careful attention and evaluation to organization, structure, and resourcing of health services. Crucially, it requires the integration of the concept and roles of new cadres, into the mainstream health system, and integrated strategic reconfiguration of healthcare teams, particularly at primary care and community levels. Without a healthcare team approach, the introduction of new cadres or delegation of tasks to related cadres will invariably remain a fragmented and becomes unsustainable add-on model.

In this context, it is observed from review literature that in several countries, task shifting has been enthusiastically and voluntarily taken up by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) with strong community links at the local level, but with limited opportunity and the potential for scaling-up to the national level, as their presence is often geographically. Task shifting holds the potential of enabling countries to build sustainable, cost-effective and equitable health care systems, not only moving forward and closer to the Millennium Development Goals [5], but also the elusive 'Health for All' goal. However, the challenge of achieving and

measuring success cannot be underestimated from humanity framework and problem-solving framework. It requires a willingness to learn from those with relevant experience (such as Brazil, Ethiopia, India, Malawi, Mozambique and Zambia) and to suspend conventional (and often conservative) wisdom on what can and cannot be done in favor of creativity, humanity, and problem-solving.

In our survey we have interviewed pharmacy undergraduates (B.Pharm), pharmacy post graduates (M.Pharm) and doctor of pharmacy students (Pharm.D) to study their curriculum based knowledge, willingness, and confidence level for taking up the task shifting responsibility during emergency period in their organization. Based on this survey, the data is analysed, and depicted in Table 1.

Table 1 : Use of pharmacy graduates for task shifting – feasibility study

Sl. No.	Alternative professionals	Knowledge	Confidence level	Time of training period
1	B.Pharm graduates	62%	58%	4 weeks
2	M.Pharm graduates	74%	76%	3 weeks
3	Pharm.D graduates	85%	90%	1 week

5. ABCD LISTING OF TASK-SHIFTING :

The predefined condition for ABCD analysis as per its framework is ABCD listing [89-99]. In this section, the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Task-shifting as an alternative survival strategy are listed.

(1) Advantages of Task-Shifting :

- It is an alternative strategy for organizations to provide minimum patient care during critical situations.
- Task shifting allows quick remedy in organizations and countries where there is an acute shortage of qualified physicians.
- Optimum health solutions to needy people at the right time.
- Task-shifting strategy improves the quality of healthcare services in the country.
- It is a positive sum game where all the stakeholders get benefit.
- Temporary Relief to unemployment problem
- Use of local paramedical personnel with additional training in chosen area based on demand.
- Job opportunity for paramedical alternative health workers.
- Quality patient care through proper training to alternative health workers.

(2) Benefits of Task-Shifting :

- Availability of alternative healthcare services.
- Better patient service using Acceptors.
- Cost-effective healthcare services.
- Creates an opportunity of increased job offerings for paramedical professionals with a comparatively better salary in developing countries.
- Long term treatment at affordable cost.
- Immediate health service to the patients.
- Task-shifting may retain the healthcare businesses locally.
- Maximize the efficiency of Alternative healthcare workers.
- Effective way of handling health professional's scarcity.

(3) Constraints of Task-Shifting :

- Difficulty in getting support from doctors/qualified physicians.
- Convincing the patients and his/her relatives on this alternative strategy.
- Convincing the society on this alternative strategy.
- Following strict policies, procedures and legal guidance to the entire process of Task-shifting.
- Maintaining quality of healthcare through Task-shifting.
- Educating & counselling the patients to know the importance of task-shifting.

(4) Disadvantages of Task-Shifting :

- Opposition from doctors/qualified physicians.
- Unqualified para-medical personnel starts treating the patients which may create legal and ethical problems.
- Societal acceptance is difficult.
- Risk to alternative healthcare workers.

6. ABCD ANALYSIS OF TASK-SHIFTING :

ABCD analysis framework methodology of strategy analysis consists of identifying various determinant issues related to Task-shifting as an alternative strategy. This is done by identifying various stakeholders of the system or strategy. Once the determinant issues are identified, the key attributes and the corresponding affecting factors under the constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are to be identified. For every affecting factors under four constructs the critical constituent elements have to be determined [100 – 113].

6.1 DETERMINANT ISSUES :

Task-shifting is an organizational strategy in a given country where availability of qualified medical professionals (physicians) are less in number and hence there is a scarcity of such professionals in healthcare organizations. This describes a situation where a patient care task normally carried out by a physician is transferred to a health professional with a different but related or lower level of education and training, or to a person trained specifically to perform

a limited task only for a short period, without having a formal health education. In such emergency situations, the healthcare organization should be able to adopt an alternative strategy to expand its workforce to meet the demand of professional physicians. The various stakeholders of such situation are the country, the healthcare organization, the physicians as donors, the alternative professionals as acceptors, the patients, the patient relatives, and the society. Thus the determinant issues related to the task-shifting are : (1) Organizational Issue, (2) Alternative Acceptors Issue, (3) Donor Physicians Issue, (4) Patients and Relatives Issue (5) Societal Issue, and (6) Country Issue. ABCD analysis framework makes use of these determinant issues for determining the affecting factors as per the four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages under each key attributes.

6.2 KEY ATTRIBUTES :

The key attributes of each determinant issues have been used for analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages which are the four major constructs of the framework. Each determinant issue may contain one or more key attributes. The ABCD constructs are determined for a given determinant issue using the identified key attributes. The key attributes for Task-shifting as an alternative survival strategy is listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Various determinant issues and key attributes for Task-shifting alternative strategy.

S. No.	Determinant Issues	Key Attributes
1	Organizational Issue	1. Quality health service
		2. Quick service
		3. Strategy
		4. Demand
2	Alternative Acceptors Issue	1. Skills
		2. Training period
		3. Attitude
3	Donor Physicians Issue	1. Intention
		2. Support
		3. Honest
		1. Service

4	Patients and Relatives Issue	2. Fear
		3. Need
		4. Timeliness
5	Societal Issue	1. Scarcity
		2. Chronic diseases
		3. Health service
6	Country Issue	1. People health
		2. Health Facility to everybody
		3. Professional manpower
		4. Utilization

6.3 FACTOR ANALYSIS USING ABCD FRAMEWORK :

The framework allows the researchers to identify the affecting factors of Task-shifting corresponding to the different key attributes under four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages as shown in table 3. Depending on the number of determinant issues and corresponding key attributes, and the number of affecting factors may vary.

Table 3 : Analysis of Task-shifting in Healthcare organizations using ABCD framework.

S. No	Determinant Issues	Key Attribute	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
1	Organizational Issue	Quality health service	Up to acceptable level	Solution to shortage of Physicians	Identifying acceptors	Risk of compromising quality
		Quick service	Healthcare support	Healthcare service to needy patients	Short training required	Slow due to carefulness
		Strategy	Alternative for scarcity	Solution to healthcare problems	Not universally acceptable	Survival strategy

		Demand	Solutions to needy people	Low cost	Preparing Acceptors	Not long term solution
2	Alternative Acceptors Issue	Skills	Opportunity to cure patients	Job opportunity	Short Training requirement	Risk and fear of legal action
		Training Period	Short term Training required	Additional knowledge	Not skilled like physician	Inadequate training
		Attitude	Positive towards patient service	Possibility to get good name/ popularity	Low quality service	Poor Quality health service
3	Donor Physicians Issue	Intention	Getting help	Relaxation during unmanageable demand	Dilemma in task-shifting	Objection
		Support	Experience sharing	Support to Acceptors	Involvement on training	Physicians non-cooperation
		Honest	Accepting the task-shifting	Solution to scarcity of Physician	Oppose from colleagues	Protests from colleagues
4	Patients and Relatives Issue	Service	Availability	Patient care	Alternative professionals	Risk factor
		Fear	Acceptance of task-shifting by patients	Additional care	Acceptance of task-shifting by Relatives	Rejection of healthcare service
		Need	Support for task-shifting	Optimum solution	No alternative	Delay in disease identification
		Timeliness	In time service	Service satisfaction	Delay in medication	Long time for curing

5	Societal Issue	Scarcity	Alternative solution may be cheap	Low cost and in time caring	Treatment by paramedical professionals	Risk in treatment
		Chronic deceases	Immediate treatment	Long term treatment at affordable cost	Delay in disease identification	Adjusting to task-shifting model
		Health service	Low cost service	Affordability for poor people	Support from qualified physicians	Compromise on quality healthcare
6	Country Issue	People health	Care in time	Good health service	Availability of acceptors with equal knowledge	Acceptance of the model
		Health Facility to everybody	Satisfactory healthcare service	At affordable cost	Convincing the organizations to follow such strategy	Model can be applicable only in certain areas of healthcare
		Professional manpower	Shifting the man power through training	Abundant manpower in healthcare sector	With compromise d quality	Competitive and trained alternatives
		Utilization	Job for paramedical professional s	Temporary Relief to unemployem t problem	Considering it as Country Policy	Acceptance of the Government and people

Depending on the number of determinant issues on a given subject of analysis, and a number of key issues/key attributes, the number of affecting factors may vary. In case of quantitative analysis, these affecting factors can be ranked by giving scores to them based on their weightage, which can be calculated using focused group method.

6.4 ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS USING ABCD FRAMEWORK :

As a part of the further analysis, the *constituent critical elements* for each construct have to be determined using its elemental analysis technique. For each ABCD construct of Task-

shifting, the critical constituent elements have to be identified and listed so that four additional tables for four sets of constituent critical elements can be developed. Further, in quantitative analysis, these critical constituent elements can be ranked based on their score/weightage in Quantitative analysis under each ABCD constructs to get quantitative result on the importance of each construct. The results on the sum of the total scores of advantages (construct A), the sum of the total scores of benefits (construct B), the sum of the total scores of constraints (construct C), and the sum of the total scores of disadvantages (construct D) have to be compared. The total sum of the scores of advantages and benefits should be more than the total sum of the scores of constraints and disadvantages, for real systems. But in this analysis we made an attempt to identify various critical constituent elements through focus group method and are listed in Tables 4 to Table 7.

Table 4: Critical Constituent Elements based on Advantages of Task-shifting as an alternative strategy for Healthcare organizations.

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
1.	Organizational Issue	Up to acceptable level	Cure of disease
			Controlling pain
		Healthcare support	Availability of acceptors
			Acceptance by patients & relatives
		Alternative for scarcity	Transferring responsibility
			Training acceptors
		Solutions to needy people	Fulfilling the demand
			Patient satisfaction
2.	Alternative Acceptors Issue	Opportunity to cure patients	Skill development
			Skill utilization
		Short term Training required	Quick training
			Confident to treatment
		Positive towards patient service	Positive Attitude
			Sympathy in patient service

			Low cost model		
3.	Donor Physicians Issue	Getting help	Helping large number of patients		
			Problem solving using alternatives		
		Experience sharing	To support Acceptors		
			To support Patients		
		Accepting the task-shifting	Honest effort in Patient care		
			Training Acceptors to Task-shift		
4.	Patients and Relatives Issue	Availability	Demand based Service to patients		
			Availability of Alternative		
		Acceptance of task-shifting by patients	Fear about Severeness of disease		
			Effort on quick recovery		
		Support for task-shifting	Urgency in patient support		
			Availability of alternative as acceptors		
		In time service	Medicine in Time		
			Cure in minimum time		
		5.	Societal Issue	Alternative solution may be cheap	Scarcity of doctors need alternative
					Task-shifting leads cheaper alternative
Immediate treatment	Care for Chronic deceases				
	Patient satisfaction				
Low cost service	Health service for everybody				
	Quality health service for Poors				
6.	Country Issue	Care in time	Satisfactory health services		
			Improved healthcare level		
		Satisfactory healthcare service	Satisfied Patients		
			Improved quality of health services		
		Shifting the man power	More Professional manpower for		

		through training	healthcare
			Quality health services
		Job for paramedical professionals	Paramedical personnel Utilization
			Utilization of country resources for alternative solution

Table 5: Critical Constituent Elements based on Benefits of the Task-shifting as an alternative strategy for Healthcare organizations.

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
1.	Organizational Issue	Solution to shortage of Physicians	Quality health services for everybody
			Attainment of organizational goal
		Healthcare service to needy patients	Quick service to Patients
			No rejection of Patients
		Solution to healthcare problems	Alternative Strategy
			Optimum solution
		Low cost	Managing the Demand
Service to poor people			
2.	Alternative Acceptors Issue	Job opportunity	Utilization of Skills
			Enhanced employment
		Additional knowledge	Confidence through Quick Training
			Trained Professionals
		Possibility to get good name/ popularity	Changed Attitude
			Positive thinking
			Opportunity to extended serving
3.	Donor Physicians Issue	Relaxation during unmanageable demand	Positive thinking for solution
			Managing the situations

		Support to Acceptors	Enhanced team members
			More Acceptors through training
		Solution to scarcity of Physician	Involvement in Training
			Creating more professionals for treating a particular disease
			Involvement in solving country problem
4.	Patients and Relatives Issue	Patient care	Quality Service
			Quick service at affordable cost
		Additional care	Additional care removes fear
			Proper counselling removes fear
		Optimum solution	Needy patients
			Proper guidance
		Service satisfaction	Healthcare in time
			Timely service through Acceptors
5.	Societal Issue	Low cost and in time caring	Optimum solution to scarcity of doctors
			Affordable cost during high demand
		Long term treatment at affordable cost	Long time satisfactory care for chronic deceases
			Avoiding self-medication in society
		Affordability for poor people	Health service to everybody
			Social justice
6.	Country Issue	Good health service	Good health index
			Healthy citizens
		At affordable cost	Low cost Health Facility to everybody
			Quality services to poor at low cost
		Abundant manpower in	Need based enhanced Professional

		healthcare sector	manpower
			Improved quality healthcare services
		Temporary Relief to unemployment problem	Enhanced employment opportunity
			Utilization of paramedical acceptors through training.

Table 6: Critical Constituent Elements based on constraints of the Task-shifting as an alternative strategy for Healthcare organizations.

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
1.	Organizational Issue	Identifying acceptors	Committed acceptors
			Qualified acceptors
		Short training required	Training the Acceptors
			Choosing right paramedical professionals
		Not universally acceptable	Acceptable Strategy
			Counselling the patients and relatives
		Preparing Acceptors	Demand based training
Confidence and hard working			
2.	Alternative Acceptors Issue	Short Training requirement	Upgrading the Skills
			Upgrading the attitude
		Not skilled like physician	Improving the skills through quick Training
			Deciding the training period
		Low quality service	Changing attitude on quality service
			Awareness of their responsibility
3.	Donor Physicians Issue	Dilemma in task-shifting	Intentional decline to train & guide
			Ethical Issue

		Involvement in training	Involved Support Training & support to Acceptors
		Oppose from colleagues	Honest Involvement Honest contribution
4.	Patients and Relatives Issue	Alternative professionals	Having doubt in quality Service
			Acceptance of health service
		Acceptance of task-shifting by Relatives	Fear on genuine service
			Accepting the ability of Alternatives
		No alternative	Need based acceptance
			Bargaining in Fee
		Delay in medication	Delay in diagnosis
			Delay in medication
5.	Societal Issue	Treatment by paramedical professionals	Scarcity of Alternatives
			Training Alternatives
		Delay in disease identification	Lack of experience in handling chronic diseases
			Scarcity in sophisticated instruments
		Support from qualified physicians	Attitude problem in health service
			Making them to contribute to solve the problem
6.	Country Issue	Availability of acceptors with equal knowledge	Compromise for People health
			Providing good quick training
		Convincing the organizations to follow such strategy	Organizational acceptance
			Arranging the alternatives by Healthcare Organizations
		With compromised quality	Patient acceptance Professional manpower

			Quality health service in the country
		Considering it as Country Policy	Upgrading the skills of Internal resources
			Utilization of internal resources

Table 7: Critical Constituent Elements based on disadvantages of the Task-shifting as an alternative strategy for Healthcare organizations.

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
1.	Organizational Issue	Risk of compromising quality	Failures in diagnostics
			Failure in medication
		Slow due to carefulness	Dissatisfaction due to slow service
			Delayed medication may increase the duration of hospitalization
		Survival strategy	Effect on brand value
			Effect on revenue
		Not long term solution	Decrease in Demand with time
			Compromising the revenue
2.	Alternative Acceptors Issue	Risk and fear of legal action	Hesitation to Accept due to lack of Skills
			Difficulty in improving and matching skills
		Inadequate training	Effect on quality treatment due to short training.
			Inability of Alternatives to improve skills during short training
		Poor Quality health service	Quality may not a criteria for Acceptors
			Affects the Task-shifting strategy

			Serving without responsibility		
3.	Donor Physicians Issue	Objection	Not supporting		
			Not involved in training		
		Physicians non-cooperation	Non-cooperation in case problems		
			Spreading gossips against task-shifting strategy		
		Protests from colleagues	Opposing the strategy		
			Agitating against the strategy due to predicted fall of their importance		
4.	Patients and Relatives Issue	Risk factor	Doubt in cure of diseases Service		
			Doubt in the ability of Acceptors		
		Rejection of healthcare service	Fear on validity of diagnostics		
			Fear in acceptance of Medication		
		Delay in disease identification	Doubt in medication process		
			Delay in cure due to problems in belief.		
		Long time for curing	Fear of delay		
			Fear of wrong treatment		
		5.	Societal Issue	Risk in treatment	More failure rates
					Adoptability
Adjusting to task-shifting model	No alternative for treatment of chronic deceases				
	Cheap service with compromised quality				
Compromise on quality healthcare	Quality of Health service may deteriorate				
	Quality of Physicians may also effected				

6.	Country Issue	Acceptance of the model	Compromise in People health
			Compromise in quality of healthcare
		Model can be applicable only in certain areas of healthcare	Imbalance in quality of healthcare services between countries
			Many organizations may take the advantage even if qualified Physicians are available.
		Competitive and trained alternatives	Dependency of alternative paramedical Professionals
			Quality of paramedical professionals
		Acceptance of the Government and people	Over utilization of Paramedical professionals
			Under utilization of Qualified Physicians

7. CONCLUSION :

Our study shows that there is a huge burden on health care professionals due to a high number of the patient load which leads to the improper patient care and degradation in the quality of health care services. Now time has approached when the term task shifting should be taken seriously especially in the health care sectors. Task shifting is a promising policy option to all the stake holders.

Based on empirical opinion study it is suggested that pharmacy graduates and post graduates are willing to take up the task shifting job, and hence it is suggested to utilize their knowledge, skills and experience in drug handling effectively as medicine prescribers and for clinical management of chronic diseases as in other developing countries as addition rather than substitution.

The ABCD analysis of task-shifting is performed in this paper by considering six determinant issues twenty-one key attributes, eighty-four affecting factors, and the analysis also brought about 172 critical constituent elements which satisfy the success. Many suggestions are also given for effective implementation of task shifting as a positive sum game in optimization of this strategic outcome.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Beaglehole, R., Epping-Jordan, J., Patel, V., Chopra, M., Ebrahim, S., Kidd, M., & Haines, A. (2008). Improving the prevention and management of chronic disease in low-income and middle-income countries: a priority for primary health care. *The Lancet*, 372(9642), 940-949.
- [2] World Health Organization. (2007). Task shifting: rational redistribution of tasks among health workforce teams: global recommendations and guidelines, Retrieved on February 6, 2017, from <http://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/43821>.
- [3] Dovlo, D. (2004). Using mid-level cadres as substitutes for internationally mobile health professionals in Africa. A desk review. *Human resources for health*, 2(1), 7.
- [4] Celletti, F., Holloway, J., De Cock, K. M., & Dybul, M. (2007). Rapid expansion of the health workforce in response to the HIV epidemic. *The New England journal of medicine*, 357(24), 2510.
- [5] Human resources for health: overcoming the crisis. *Global Equity Initiative*. (2004). Retrieved on February 6, 2017, from http://www.who.int/hrh/documents/JLi_hrh_report.pdf.
- [6] World Medical Association World Medical Association Resolutions on task shifting from the medical profession. Retrieved on February 6, 2017, from <http://www.wma.net/en/30publications/10policies/t4/index.html>.
- [7] Buttorff, C., Hock, R. S., Weiss, H. A., Naik, S., Araya, R., Kirkwood, B. R., & Patel, V. (2012). Economic evaluation of a task-shifting intervention for common mental disorders in India. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 90(11), 813- 821.
- [8] World Health Organization. (2012). Task shifting to tackle health worker shortages. 2007. *Geneva: World Health Organization HIV/AIDS Programme*. Retrieved on February 6, 2017, from http://www.who.int/healthsystems/task_shifting_booklet.pdf.
- [9] Mdege, N. D., Chindove, S., & Ali, S. (2012). The effectiveness and cost implications of task-shifting in the delivery of antiretroviral therapy to HIV-infected patients: a systematic review. *Health policy and planning*, czs058.
- [10] Labhardt, N. D., Balo, J. R., Ndam, M., Manga, E., & Stoll, B. (2011). Improved retention rates with low- cost interventions in hypertension and diabetes management in a rural African environment of nurse- led care: a cluster- randomised trial. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 16(10), 1276-1284.
- [11] Rahman, A., Malik, A., Sikander, S., Roberts, C., & Creed, F. (2008). Cognitive behaviour therapy-based intervention by community health workers for mothers with depression and their infants in rural Pakistan: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 372(9642), 902-909.
- [12] Petersen, I., S, Sebunnya, J., Bhana, A., & Baillie, K. (2011). Lessons from case studies of integrating mental health into primary health care in South Africa and Uganda. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, 5(1), 8.

- [13] World Health Organization, World Organization of National Colleges, & Academic Associations of General Practitioners/Family Physicians. (2008). Integrating mental health into primary care: a global perspective. World Health Organization. Retrieved on February 6, 2017 from http://www.who.int/mental_health/policy/services/mentalhealthintopriarycare/en/
- [14] Bolton P, Bass J, Neugebauer R, Verdeli H, Clougherty KF, Wickramaratne P et al. (2003). Group interpersonal psychotherapy for depression in rural Uganda: a randomized controlled trial. *JAMA*, 289, 3117–3124. doi:10.1001/jama.289.23.3117.
- [15] Bass J, Neugebauer R, Clougherty KF, Verdeli H, Wickramaratne P, Ndogoni L et al. (2006). Group interpersonal psychotherapy for depression in rural Uganda: 6-month outcomes: randomised controlled trial. *Br J Psychiatry*, 188, 567– 573. doi:10.1192/bjp.188.6.567.
- [16] Araya, R., Flynn, T., Rojas, G., Fritsch, R., & Simon, G. (2006). Cost-effectiveness of a primary care treatment program for depression in low-income women in Santiago, Chile. *American journal of psychiatry*, 163(8), 1379-1387.
- [17] McPake, B., & Mensah, K. (2008). Task-shifting in Healthcare in resource-poor countries. *The Lancet*, 372(9642), 870-871.
- [18] Zimmerman, M. (2008). Task-shifting and innovative medical education--moving outside the box to serve rural Nepal. *JNMA; journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, 48(176), 340-343.
- [19] Lehmann, U., Van Damme, W., Barten, F., & Sanders, D. (2009). Task-shifting: the answer to the human resources crisis in Africa. *Human resources for health*, 7(1), 49.
- [20] Morris, M. B., Chapula, B. T., Chi, B. H., Mwangi, A., Chi, H. F., Mwanza, J. & Reid, S. E. (2009). Use of task-shifting to rapidly scale-up HIV treatment services: experiences from Lusaka, Zambia. *BMC health services research*, 9(1), 5.
- [21] Shumbusho, F., Van Griensven, J., Lowrance, D., Turate, I., Weaver, M. A., Price, J., & Binagwaho, A. (2009). Task-shifting for scale-up of HIV care: evaluation of nurse-centered antiretroviral treatment at rural health centers in Rwanda. *PLoS medicine*, 6(10), e1000163.
- [22] De Brouwere, V., Dieng, T., Diadiou, M., Witter, S., & Denerville, E. (2009). Task-shifting for emergency obstetric surgery in district hospitals in Senegal. *Reproductive Health Matters*, 17(33), 32-44.
- [23] Chu, K., Rosseel, P., Gielis, P., & Ford, N. (2009). Surgical Task-shifting in sub-Saharan Africa. *PLoS medicine*, 6(5), e1000078.
- [24] Lekoubou, A., Awah, P., Fezeu, L., Sobngwi, E., & Kengne, A. P. (2010). Hypertension, diabetes mellitus and Task-shifting in their management in sub-Saharan Africa. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 7(2), 353-363.
- [25] McCollum, E. D., Preidis, G. A., Kabue, M. M., Singogo, E. B., Mwansambo, C., Kazembe, P. N., & Kline, M. W. (2010). Task-shifting routine inpatient pediatric HIV testing improves program outcomes in urban Malawi: a retrospective observational study. *PloS one*, 5(3), e9626.

- [26] Callaghan, M., Ford, N., & Schneider, H. (2010). A systematic review of task-shifting for HIV treatment and care in Africa. *Human resources for health*, 8(1), 8.
- [27] Ivers, L. C., Jerome, J. G., Cullen, K. A., Lambert, W., Celletti, F., & Samb, B. (2011). Task-shifting in HIV care: a case study of nurse-centered community-based care in rural Haiti. *PLoS One*, 6(5), e19276.
- [28] Gessesew, A., Ab Barnabas, G., Prata, N., & Weidert, K. (2011). Task-shifting and sharing in Tigray, Ethiopia, to achieve comprehensive emergency obstetric care. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 113(1), 28-31.
- [29] Nabudere, H., Asiimwe, D., & Mijumbi, R. (2011). Task-shifting in maternal and child Healthcare: an evidence brief for Uganda. *International journal of technology assessment in Healthcare*, 27(2), 173-179.
- [30] Dambisya, Y. M., & Matinhure, S. (2012). Policy and programmatic implications of Task-shifting in Uganda: a case study. *BMC health services research*, 12(1), 61.
- [31] Ferrinho, P., Sidat, M., Goma, F., & Dussault, G. (2012). Task-shifting: experiences and opinions of health workers in Mozambique and Zambia. *Human resources for health*, 10(1), 34.
- [32] Ford, N., Chu, K., & Mills, E. J. (2012). Safety of task-shifting for male medical circumcision: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Aids*, 26(5), 559-566.
- [33] Mdege, N. D., Chindove, S., & Ali, S. (2012). The effectiveness and cost implications of task-shifting in the delivery of antiretroviral therapy to HIV-infected patients: a systematic review. *Health policy and planning*, 28(3), 223-236.
- [34] Buttorff, C., Hock, R. S., Weiss, H. A., Naik, S., Araya, R., Kirkwood, B. R. ...& Patel, V. (2012). Economic evaluation of a task-shifting intervention for common mental disorders in India. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 90(11), 813-821
- [35] Dawson, A. J., Buchan, J., Duffield, C., Homer, C. S., & Wijewardena, K. (2013). Task-shifting and sharing in maternal and reproductive health in low-income countries: a narrative synthesis of current evidence. *Health policy and planning*, 29(3), 396-408.
- [36] Guilbert, E. R., Robitaille, J., Guilbert, A. C., & Morin, D. (2013). Challenges of implementing task-shifting in contraceptive care an experience in Quebec, Canada. *Contraception*, 88(5), 587-590.
- [37] FIGO Committee for the Ethical Aspects of Human Reproduction and Women's Health. (2013). Task-shifting in obstetric care. *International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 2(120), 206-207.
- [38] Iwu, E. N., & Holzemer, W. L. (2014). Task-shifting of HIV management from doctors to nurses in Africa: Clinical outcomes and evidence on nurse self-efficacy and job satisfaction. *AIDS care*, 26(1), 42-52.
- [39] Joshi, R., Alim, M., Kengne, A. P., Jan, S., Maulik, P. K., Peiris, D., & Patel, A. A. (2014). Task-shifting for non-communicable disease management in low and middle income countries—a systematic review. *PloS one*, 9(8), e103754.

- [40] Kredo, T., Adeniyi, F. B., Bateganya, M., & Pienaar, E. D. (2014). Task-shifting from doctors to non- doctors for initiation and maintenance of antiretroviral therapy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 1(7), 7331. DOI:10.1002/14651858.CD007331.pub3.
- [41] Maier, C. B. (2015). The role of governance in implementing task-shifting from physicians to nurses in advanced roles in Europe, US, Canada, New Zealand and Australia. *Health policy*, 119(12), 1627-1635.
- [42] Gichangi, M., Kalua, K., Barassa, E., Eliah, E., Lewallen, S., & Courtright, P. (2015). Task-shifting for eye care in eastern Africa: general nurses as trichiasis surgeons in Kenya, Malawi, and Tanzania. *Ophthalmic epidemiology*, 22(3), 226-230.
- [43] Crowley, T., & Mayers, P. (2015). Trends in Task-shifting in HIV treatment in Africa: Effectiveness, challenges and acceptability to the health professions. *African journal of primary Healthcare & family medicine*, 7(1), 1-9.
- [44] Agyapong, V. I., Osei, A., Farren, C. K., & Mcauliffe, E. (2015). Task-shifting of mental Healthcare services in Ghana: ease of referral, perception and concerns of stakeholders about quality of care. *International Journal for Quality in Healthcare*, 27(5), 377-383.
- [45] Jayasekera, C. R., Perumpail, R. B., Chao, D. T., Pham, E. A., Agarwal, A., Wong, R. J., & Ahmed, A. (2015). Task-shifting: an approach to decentralized hepatitis C treatment in medically underserved areas. *Digestive diseases and sciences*, 60(12), 3552-3557.
- [46] Gupta, B., Huckman, R. S., & Khanna, T. (2015). Task-shifting in surgery: lessons from an Indian Heart Hospital. In *Healthcare*, 3(4), 245-250.
- [47] Akinyemi, R. O., Owolabi, M. O., Adebayo, P. B., Akinyemi, J. O., Otubogun, F. M., Uvere, E., & Ogun, S. A. (2015). Task-shifting training improves stroke knowledge among Nigerian non-neurologist health workers. *Journal of the neurological sciences*, 359(1), 112-116.
- [48] Bhushan, H., & Bhardwaj, A. (2015). Task-shifting: A key strategy in the multipronged approach to reduce maternal mortality in India. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 131(S1).
- [49] Maier, C. B., & Aiken, L. H. (2016). Task-shifting from physicians to nurses in primary care in 39 countries: a cross-country comparative study. *The European Journal of Public Health*, 26(6), 927-934.
- [50] Santos, P. F., Wainberg, M. L., Caldas-de-Almeida, J. M., Saraceno, B., & de Jesus Mari, J. (2016). Overview of the mental health system in Mozambique: addressing the treatment gap with a task-shifting strategy in primary care. *International journal of mental health systems*, 10(1), 1.
- [51] Jayasekera, C. R., Arora, S., & Ahmed, A. (2016). Hepatitis C treatment delivery mandates optimizing available Healthcare human resources: a case for Task-shifting. *Jama*, 315(18), 1947-1948.
- [52] Some, D., Edwards, J. K., Reid, T., Van den Bergh, R., Kosgei, R. J., Wilkinson, E., & Kibachio, J. (2016). Task-shifting the management of non-communicable diseases to nurses in Kibera, Kenya: does it work. *PloS one*, 11(1), e0145634.

- [53] Hadorn, F., Comte, P., Foucault, E., Morin, D., & Hugli, O. (2016). Task-shifting Using a Pain Management Protocol in an Emergency Care Service: Nurses' Perception through the Eye of the Rogers's Diffusion of Innovation Theory. *Pain Management Nursing*, 17(1), 80-87.
- [54] Yoo, E. R., Perumpail, R. B., Cholanketil, G., Jayasekera, C. R., & Ahmed, A. (2016). Task-shifting-A practical strategy to improve the global access to treatment for chronic hepatitis C. *International journal of nursing studies*, 62, 168.
- [55] Kayingo, G. (2016). Task-shifting and capacity building for non-communicable diseases in Uganda. *Annals of Global Health*, 82(3), 370.
- [56] Gyamfi, J., Plange-Rhule, J., Iwelunmor, J., Lee, D., Blackstone, S. R., Mitchell, A. ...& Cooper, R. (2017). Training nurses in task-shifting strategies for the management and control of hypertension in Ghana: a mixed-methods study. *BMC health services research*, 17(1), 104.
- [57] Bischoff, R., Springer, P., Taylor, N., & Cruickshank, K. (2017). The Experiences of Task-shifting to Reduce Mental Health Disparities in Underserved, Rural Communities. *Annals of Global Health*, 83(1), 182.
- [58] Magidson, J. F., Gouse, H., Psaros, C., Remmert, J. E., O'Cleirigh, C., & Safren, S. A. (2017). Task-shifting and Delivery of Behavioral Medicine Interventions in Resource-Poor Global Settings: HIV/AIDS Treatment in sub-Saharan Africa. In *The Massachusetts General Hospital Handbook of Behavioral Medicine* (pp. 297-320). Springer International Publishing.
- [59] Iwelunmor, J., Gyamfi, J., Plange-Rhule, J., Blackstone, S., Quakyi, N. K., Ntim, M. ...& Ogedegbe, G. (2017). Exploring stakeholders' perceptions of a task-shifting strategy for hypertension control in Ghana: a qualitative study. *BMC public health*, 17(1), 216.
- [60] Keller, B., McCarthy, E., Vosburg, K. B., Musonda, M., Mwila, J., van den Broek, J. W., & Walsh, F. J. (2017). Task-shifting impact of introducing a pilot community health worker cadre into Zambia's public sector health workforce. *PloS one*, 12(8), e0181740.
- [61] Sanyahumbi, A. S., Sable, C. A., Karlsten, M., Hosseinipour, M. C., Kazembe, P. N., Minard, C. G., & Penny, D. J. (2017). Task-shifting to clinical officer-led echocardiography screening for detecting rheumatic heart disease in Malawi, Africa. *Cardiology in the Young*, 27(6), 1133-1139.
- [62] Landes, M., Thompson, C., Mwinjiwa, E., Thaulo, E., Gondwe, C., Akello, H., & Chan, A. K. (2017). Task-shifting of triage to peer expert informal care providers at a tertiary referral HIV clinic in Malawi: a cross-sectional operational evaluation. *BMC health services research*, 17(1), 341.
- [63] Kattakuzhy, S., Gross, C., Emmanuel, B., Teferi, G., Jenkins, V., Silk, R., & Price, A. (2017). Expansion of Treatment for Hepatitis C Virus Infection by Task-shifting to Community-based Nonspecialist Providers: A Nonrandomized Clinical Trial. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 167(5), 311-318.
- [64] Galárraga, O., Gao, B., Gakinya, B. N., Klein, D. A., Wamai, R. G., Sidle, J. E., & Papas, R. K. (2017). Task-shifting alcohol interventions for HIV+ persons in Kenya: a cost-benefit analysis. *BMC health services research*, 17(1), 239.
- [65] Okyere, E., Mwanri, L., & Ward, P. (2017). Is task-shifting a solution to the health workers' shortage in Northern Ghana. *PloS one*, 12(3), e0174631.

- [66] Aithal, Architha & Jha, Ateendra, (2017). An Empirical Study on the Importance of Task-shifting in Current Healthcare System. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 1(1), 14-25, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.438334>.
- [67] Aithal, Architha & Jha, Ateendra, Task-shifting: A Need for Current Healthcare System (2017). *Saudi Journal of Medicine and Pharmaceutics*, ISSN: 2413-4910 (Online), Vol. 3. No. 3, pp. 1-12. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.21276/sjmpps.2017.3.3.1>.
- [68] Mumtaz, Z., & Patterson, P. (2017). Does Task-shifting among parts of a weak health system help. *The Lancet Global Health*, 5(8), e734-e735.
- [69] Spies, L. A. (2016). An exploratory descriptive study on Task-shifting in East Africa. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 39(2), E44-E53.
- [70] Mbeye, N. M., Adetokunboh, O., Negussie, E., Kredo, T., & Wiysonge, C. S. (2017). Shifting tasks from pharmacy to non-pharmacy personnel for providing antiretroviral therapy to people living with HIV: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 7(8), e015072.
- [71] Callaghan, M., Ford, N., & Schneider, H. (2010). A systematic review of task-shifting for HIV treatment and care in Africa. *Human resources for health*, 8(1), 8.
- [72] Fulton, B. D., Scheffler, R. M., Sparkes, S. P., Auh, E. Y., Vujicic, M., & Soucat, A. (2011). Health workforce skill mix and Task-shifting in low income countries: a review of recent evidence. *Human resources for health*, 9(1), 1.
- [73] Emdin, C. A., & Millson, P. (2012). A systematic review evaluating the impact of Task-shifting on access to antiretroviral therapy in sub-Saharan Africa. *African health sciences*, 12(3), 318-324.
- [74] Mdege, N. D., Chindove, S., & Ali, S. (2012). The effectiveness and cost implications of task-shifting in the delivery of antiretroviral therapy to HIV-infected patients: a systematic review. *Health policy and planning*, 28(3), 223-236.
- [75] Ford, N., Chu, K., & Mills, E. J. (2012). Safety of task-shifting for male medical circumcision: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Aids*, 26(5), 559-566.
- [76] Colvin, C. J., de Heer, J., Winterton, L., Mellenkamp, M., Glenton, C., Noyes, J. ...& Rashidian, A. (2013). A systematic review of qualitative evidence on barriers and facilitators to the implementation of task-shifting in midwifery services. *Midwifery*, 29(10), 1211-1221.
- [77] Padmanathan, P., & De Silva, M. J. (2013). The acceptability and feasibility of task-sharing for mental healthcare in low and middle income countries: a systematic review. *Social science & medicine*, 97, 82-86.
- [78] Ogedegbe, G., Gyamfi, J., Plange-Rhule, J., Surkis, A., Rosenthal, D. M., Airhihenbuwa, C., & Cooper, R. (2014). Task-shifting interventions for cardiovascular risk reduction in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *BMJ open*, 4(10), e005983.
- [79] Penazzato, M., Davies, M. A., Apollo, T., Negussie, E., & Ford, N. (2014). Task-shifting for the delivery of pediatric antiretroviral treatment: a systematic review. *JAIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 65(4), 414-422.

- [80] Martínez-González, N. A., Rosemann, T., Djalali, S., Huber-Geismann, F., & Tandjung, R. (2015). Task-shifting from physicians to nurses in primary care and its impact on resource utilization: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 72(4), 395-418.
- [81] Martínez-González, N. A., Tandjung, R., Djalali, S., & Rosemann, T. (2015). The impact of physician–nurse Task-shifting in primary care on the course of disease: a systematic review. *Human resources for health*, 13(1), 55.
- [82] Polus, S., Lewin, S., Glenton, C., Lerberg, P. M., Rehfuess, E., & Gülmezoglu, A. M. (2015). Optimizing the delivery of contraceptives in low-and middle-income countries through Task-shifting: a systematic review of effectiveness and safety. *Reproductive health*, 12(1), 27.
- [83] Crowley, T., & Mayers, P. (2015). Trends in Task-shifting in HIV treatment in Africa: Effectiveness, challenges and acceptability to the health professions. *African journal of primary Healthcare & family medicine*, 7(1), 1-9.
- [84] Federspiel, F., Mukhopadhyay, S., Milsom, P., Scott, J. W., Riesel, J. N., & Meara, J. G. (2015). Global surgical and anaesthetic Task-shifting: a systematic literature review and survey. *The Lancet*, 385, S46.
- [85] Lee, E. S., Vedanthan, R., Jeemon, P., Kamano, J. H., Kudesia, P., Rajan, V., & Moran, A. E. (2016). Quality improvement for cardiovascular disease care in low-and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *PloS one*, 11(6), e0157036. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0157036>.
- [86] Maier, C. B., & Aiken, L. H. (2016). Task-shifting from physicians to nurses in primary care in 39 countries: a cross-country comparative study. *The European Journal of Public Health*, 26(6), 927-934.
- [87] Seidman, G., & Atun, R. (2017). Does Task-shifting yield cost savings and improve efficiency for health systems? A systematic review of evidence from low-income and middle-income countries. *Human resources for health*, 15(1), 29.
- [88] Mbeye, N. M., Adetokunboh, O., Negussie, E., Kredo, T., & Wiysonge, C. S. (2017). Shifting tasks from pharmacy to non-pharmacy personnel for providing antiretroviral therapy to people living with HIV: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 7(8), e015072.
- [89] Reshma, Aithal P. S., Shailashree V T, & Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). An Empirical study on working from home – A popular E-business model, *International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research*, 2(2), 12-18. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164429>.
- [90] Aithal, P. S., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Theory A for Optimizing Human Productivity, *IRA International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 4(3), 526-535. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v4.n3.p2>.
- [91] Reshma, Aithal, P. S & Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). Relevance of On-line Office Administration through Working from Home in Future Education System. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management*, 4(4), 44 – 53. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163882>.

- [92] Padmanabha Shenoy, and Aithal P. S., (2016). A Study on History of Paper and possible Paper Free World. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 337-355. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161141>.
- [93] Aithal, P.S., (2015). Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities – A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 4(12), 106-122. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163884>.
- [94] Aithal P. S., and Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016). Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 278-284. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161046>.
- [95] Varun Shenoy and Aithal, P. S. (2016). Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 766 – 776. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160966>.
- [96] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). A New Model for Commercialization of Nanotechnology Products and Services. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development*, 1(1), 84-93. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163536>.
- [97] Shubrajyotsna Aithal & Aithal, P. S., (2016). Student Centric Learning through Planned Hardwork - An Innovative Model. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 886-898. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61830>.
- [98] Sridhar Acharya & Aithal, P. S. (2017). Electricity from Microbial Fuel Cell- Challenges in Implementing the Cell in Rural India. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research (IJAASR)*, 2(1), 90-93. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.569764>.
- [99] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Comparative Study of Various Research Indices used to measure quality of Research Publications. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research (IJAASR)*, 2(1), 81-89. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.569763>.
- [100] Aithal, P. S., (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, Business Strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>.
- [101] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Application of ABCD Analysis Model for Black Ocean Strategy. *International Journal of Applied Research (IJAR)*, 1(10), 331-337. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163424>.
- [102] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 11-24. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.154233>.
- [103] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V.T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 30 - 44. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.154272>.
- [104] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 5(4), 159-170. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161111>.

- [105] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M., (2016). The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 389 – 402. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161077>.
- [106] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T. & Suresh Kumar, P. M., (2016). Analysis of ABC Model of Annual Research Productivity using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 846-858. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62022>.
- [107] Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, & Aithal, P. S., (2016), ABCD analysis of Dye doped Polymers for Photonic Applications. *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 358-378. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jas.v4.n3.p1>.
- [108] Varun Shenoy, & Aithal P. S., (2016). ABCD Analysis of On-line Campus Placement Model, *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 5(2), 227-244. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v5.n2.p3>.
- [109] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree V. T. & Suresh Kumar P.M. (2016). Factors & Elemental Analysis of Six Thinking Hats Technique using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET)*, 1(1), 85-95. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.240259>.
- [110] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). CCE Approach through ABCD Analysis of ‘Theory A’ on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)* 1(1), 169-185. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164704>.
- [111] Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD Analysis of Recently Announced New Research Indices. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(1), 65-76. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.583644>.
- [112] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Factor Analysis based on ABCD Framework on Recently Announced New Research Indices, *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 1(1), 82-94. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.584105>.
- [113] Aithal, P. S., (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891621>.